

Marru(convert): Structure Data Creation from Unstructured Text for Fine-tuning Large Language Models in Indian Languages

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Abstract—This paper, we present a methodology for converting unstructured text into a structured question-and-answer format, specifically targeting 11 Indian languages. The scarcity of question-and-answer datasets for these languages poses a significant challenge for fine-tuning Large Language Models (LLMs) for specific tasks. We employed a ternary quantized model based on the LLaMA-2 architecture to achieve this conversion efficiently. Our model, BitNet 1.58, leverages a unique computation paradigm, reducing memory consumption and enhancing computational efficiency. The dataset was created in the Alpaca format and trained on 47 million data tokens over 3 epochs. Evaluation challenges were addressed using ^[3]Grice’s Maxims and AI-assisted evaluation techniques. The research demonstrates significant potential for improving data quality and expanding usability across more languages.

I. INTRODUCTION

Large Language Models (LLMs) have shown remarkable capabilities in various natural language processing tasks, including text generation, translation, summarization, and question answering. These models, such as GPT-4, Claude, Gemini, and their successors, rely heavily on the availability of extensive, high-quality datasets tailored to specific tasks to achieve optimal performance.

However, the availability of such datasets is not uniform across all languages. For many Indian languages, there is a significant scarcity of task-specific datasets, especially in the question-and-answer format. This scarcity hampers the ability to fine-tune LLMs effectively for these languages, limiting their applicability and performance.

This research aims to address this critical gap by developing a methodology to convert unstructured text into a structured question-and-answer format. By leveraging existing textual data sources such as news articles, documents, and other forms of written content, we propose a system that can automatically generate high-quality question-and-answer pairs.

Our approach involves using advanced techniques for text chunking and retrieval, followed by the application of a ternary quantized model based on the LLaMA-2 architecture. By converting unstructured text into a structured format, we can elevate the performance of LLMs. Fine-tuning models with high-quality structured data improves the quality of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) systems. Additionally, introducing hypotheses in the first step of the RAG process further enhances the retrieval quality. This structured data serves as a robust foundation for various applications, improving not only the accuracy of LLMs in generating relevant responses

but also their efficiency in diverse linguistic and contextual scenarios.

The resulting structured datasets will enable the fine-tuning of LLMs, enhancing their performance in various applications for Indian languages. This work not only contributes to the field of natural language processing but also promotes the inclusion and development of technological resources for underrepresented languages.

By addressing the lack of structured datasets for Indian languages, this research aims to bridge the gap in data availability, thereby enabling LLMs to better understand and process these languages. This has significant implications for various applications, including educational tools, healthcare, legal and financial services, and more, ultimately contributing to the technological advancement and linguistic inclusivity of these languages.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

The foundation of this research is the collection of diverse and extensive unstructured text data. To ensure a comprehensive dataset, we sourced text from a variety of domains including news articles, academic papers, government documents, literature, and other publicly available textual information.

News Articles: News articles are a rich source of information, offering a wide range of topics and writing styles. They provide current and historical perspectives on events, which are invaluable for generating relevant and contextually accurate question-and-answer pairs.

Academic Papers: Academic papers provide in-depth and structured content, often containing complex information that can be useful for generating high-quality question-and-answer pairs. We accessed academic databases and institutional repositories to collect papers written in the target languages, focusing on various fields such as science, technology, social sciences, and humanities.

Government Documents: Government documents, including policy papers, reports, and official statements, are another valuable source of structured information. These documents often contain factual and procedural information, which can be effectively transformed into question-and-answer pairs. We obtained documents from government portals and archives.

Literature and Other Textual Information: To ensure linguistic diversity and richness, we included literary works such as novels, short stories, and essays. These sources provide a variety of narrative styles and complex sentence structures, enhancing the quality and diversity of the generated question-and-answer pairs. Additionally, we incorporated other publicly available textual information from blogs, forums, and social media.

The collected data was then preprocessed to remove any noise, irrelevant information, and duplicate entries. This preprocessing step included tasks such as language detection, sentence segmentation, and text normalization. By ensuring the quality and relevance of the data, we laid a strong foundation for the subsequent steps of text chunking, model training, and question-and-answer generation.

B. Parent-Child Chunking

Fig. 1. Parent-Child Chunking

The first step in our methodology involved parent-child text chunking, which splits complex long-context text into smaller, manageable chunks. This method helps in creating a more extensive and detailed dataset by breaking down original documents into smaller, contextually relevant pieces.

The Concept of Parent and Child Chunks:

- **Parent Chunk:** The process begins with the segmentation of an original document into comprehensive sections, referred to as parent chunks. Each parent chunk represents a substantial unit of content, such as a lengthy article, report, or document. These parent chunks contain a broad context that encompasses various themes and topics within the document. For instance, a research paper might be segmented into parent chunks, encapsulating sections like introduction, methodology, results, and conclusion.
- **Segmentation of Parent Chunks into Child Chunks:** To create more detailed and manageable pieces of data, each parent chunk is further segmented into smaller sections, known as child chunks. Each child chunk captures a specific aspect or section of the parent chunk. For example, in a lengthy news article, different paragraphs or sections might be segmented into child chunks, each focusing on a specific part of the story.
- **Maintaining Contextual Integrity:** While segmenting the parent chunk into child chunks, it is crucial to maintain the contextual integrity of each segment. This means that each child chunk should be contextually self-contained but also retain the ability to reference the broader context

provided by the parent chunk. This ensures that the detailed information within the child chunk is accurate and relevant while preserving the overall context of the original document.

- **Hierarchical Structure:** The parent-child chunking method establishes a hierarchical structure where the parent chunk serves as the primary source of comprehensive information, and the child chunks serve as detailed, context-specific segments. This hierarchical approach allows for efficient data management and retrieval, facilitating the creation of high-quality question-and-answer pairs.
- **Data Granularity:** By breaking down the parent chunk into child chunks, we achieve a higher level of data granularity. This granularity is essential for capturing nuanced information and generating specific question-and-answer pairs. For instance, a child chunk derived from a scientific paper’s methodology section can generate questions related to experimental procedures, while another child chunk from the results section can focus on the findings.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** The parent-child chunking method is scalable and flexible, making it applicable to a wide range of document types and lengths. Whether dealing with short news articles or extensive research reports, this method can be adapted to suit the document’s complexity and the desired level of detail for the generated data.
- **Example of Parent-Child Chunking:** Consider a detailed government report on environmental policies. The parent chunk would be an entire section of the report, such as policy introduction, specific regulations, impact assessments, or future recommendations. Each of these sections can be further segmented into child chunks, such as individual regulations or specific impact studies. This segmentation allows for the creation of targeted question-and-answer pairs related to specific policies or environmental impacts while retaining the comprehensive context of the full report.

Cosine Similarity for Data Enhancement:

Fig. 2. Chunking Process and Cosine Similarity

After segmenting the original document into parent and child chunks, the next step involves calculating the cosine similarity of each chunk to identify and group similar chunks. This process enhances the quality and relevance of the generated question-and-answer pairs.

- **Embedding Child Chunks:** Each child chunk is converted into an embedding, a numerical representation that captures the semantic meaning of the text. These embeddings facilitate the comparison of different chunks based on their content.
- **Calculating Cosine Similarity:** Cosine similarity measures the cosine of the angle between two non-zero vectors, providing a metric to gauge the similarity between different embeddings. By comparing the embeddings of child chunks, we identify chunks that are contextually similar.
- **Grouping Similar Chunks:** Chunks with high cosine similarity are grouped together. This grouping allows us to gather contextually related chunks, ensuring that the generated question-and-answer pairs are coherent and contextually rich.
- **Generating Question-and-Answer Pairs:** The grouped similar chunks are then used to generate question-and-answer pairs. This approach leverages the detailed context of similar chunks, improving the relevance and accuracy of the generated data.

By leveraging the parent-child chunking method and cosine similarity, we ensure that the data created is not only precise and contextually rich but also scalable and applicable to various real-world scenarios. This method allows for the development of robust and versatile datasets, facilitating the fine-tuning of LLMs for multiple languages and enhancing their usability across different applications.

C. Training

The training phase of our project was crucial to transforming the collected and structured data into a highly functional model capable of generating question-and-answer pairs in multiple Indian languages. Here, we outline the comprehensive steps and methodologies employed in this phase.

1) *Dataset and Format:* To train the model, we used the `ai4bharat/IndicQuestionGeneration` dataset. This dataset was formatted into the Alpaca format, which is designed to facilitate efficient training of language models.

2) *Model Architecture and Training Process:* We employed a ternary quantized model based on the LLaMA-2 architecture, specifically designed to optimize memory consumption and computational efficiency. The model operates using a ^[1]1.58-bit architecture, where each parameter takes on values from $\{-1, 0, 1\}$. This innovative design allows for substantial savings in energy consumption and enhances the throughput and latency of the model.

Training Parameters:

Fig. 3. Train/Loss of the Model

- **Data Tokens:** The model was trained on an extensive dataset comprising 47 million data tokens. This large dataset size was essential for capturing the diverse linguistic nuances present in the 11 target Indian languages.
- **Epochs:** The training process spanned 3 epochs, lasting over 12 hours. This prolonged training duration was necessary to ensure that the model could adequately learn and generalize from the dataset.
- **Model Sizes:** We experimented with 70M parameter model. Despite its relatively small size, the 70M model demonstrated promising results, highlighting the efficiency and effectiveness of the ternary quantized approach.

In summary, the training phase was a pivotal component of our research, leveraging innovative model architectures and extensive datasets to create a robust and efficient model capable of generating high-quality question-and-answer pairs in multiple Indian languages. The successful completion of this phase set the stage for the subsequent evaluation and application of the model.

III. EVALUATION

A. Evaluation Metrics

Evaluating the performance of our model in generating question-and-answer pairs across 11 Indian languages presented unique challenges. Conventional metrics for summarization and question-answer generation, such as ^[20]BLEU, ^[18]ROUGE, ^[21]METEOR, ^[22]FactCC, Perplexity and ^[23]QAFactEval were not directly applicable to our specific use case. Therefore, we adopted a multifaceted evaluation approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative measures to ensure comprehensive assessment of the model's performance.

1) *Limitations of Conventional Metrics:* Traditional evaluation metrics are commonly used for tasks such as machine translation, summarization, and text generation. While these metrics are effective for evaluating the overlap between generated text and reference text, they fall short in capturing the nuances of quality and relevance in question-answer generation.

Despite the utility of these metrics in their respective domains, they are limited in evaluating the quality and relevance of generated question-and-answer pairs for several reasons:

- They primarily focus on surface-level text overlap and do not account for the contextual relevance or coherence of the responses.
- They are not designed to measure the appropriateness or informativeness of answers within a specific context, which is crucial for high-quality question-answer generation.
- These metrics fail to capture the relational and interactional aspects of question-answer pairs, such as the logical flow and contextual relevance of the responses.

Due to these limitations, alternative evaluation frameworks, such as ^[3]Grice’s Maxims, were employed to provide a more holistic and accurate assessment of the model’s performance in generating question-answer pairs.

2) *Adoption of Grice’s Maxims:* To address these limitations, we employed ^[3]Grice’s Maxims as the primary framework for evaluating the model’s responses. ^[3]Grice’s Maxims offer a set of conversational principles that provide a robust foundation for assessing the quality and effectiveness of generated question-answer pairs. The four maxims include:

- **Maxim of Quantity:** Ensuring the response is as informative as necessary, without providing excessive information. This helps in evaluating whether the generated answers are concise and relevant.
- **Maxim of Quality:** Ensuring the response is truthful and supported by evidence. This maxim helps in assessing the factual accuracy and reliability of the generated answers.
- **Maxim of Relation:** Ensuring the response is relevant to the context and the question posed. This is crucial for evaluating the contextual appropriateness and relevance of the answers.
- **Maxim of Manner:** Ensuring the response is clear, unambiguous, and well-organized. This maxim helps in evaluating the clarity and coherence of the generated answers.

3) *Manual Evaluation:* To complement the evaluation using ^[3]Grice’s Maxims, we also conducted manual evaluations of the model’s responses. This involved:

- **Human Reviewers:** A team of bilingual experts reviewed a sample of the generated question-answer pairs in each of the 11 target languages. They assessed the responses based on the principles of ^[3]Grice’s Maxims, providing qualitative feedback on the accuracy, relevance, and clarity of the answers.
- **Evaluation Criteria:** Reviewers rated each response on a scale from 0 to 1 for each of the four maxims. This provided a structured and quantifiable measure of the model’s performance across different languages and contexts.

B. AI-Assisted Evaluation

To enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of our evaluation process, we leveraged AI-assisted techniques using advanced commercially available models such as Claude, and

Gemini. This approach provided an efficient and scalable means of assessing the quality of the generated question-and-answer pairs across multiple languages.

1) *Few-Shot Learning Techniques:* To tailor these AI models for our specific evaluation needs, we employed few-shot learning techniques. Few-shot learning involves providing the models with a small number of examples to illustrate the desired task, enabling them to generalize and apply this understanding to new data:

- **Example-Based Training:** We curated a set of high-quality question-and-answer pairs, each accompanied by detailed annotations explaining why they were exemplary. These examples covered various contexts and languages, ensuring the models could handle diverse scenarios.
- **Instructional Prompts:** The AI models were given clear instructional prompts based on ^[3]Grice’s Maxims. For instance, they were instructed to evaluate responses based on informativeness, truthfulness, relevance, and clarity. These prompts guided the models in scoring the outputs effectively.
- **Iterative Refinement:** The few-shot learning process was iterative. We continually refined the examples and instructions based on the initial evaluation results, ensuring the models’ scoring criteria aligned closely with our evaluation standards.

2) *Evaluation Process:* The evaluation process involved several key steps to ensure thorough and accurate assessment:

- **Scoring Outputs:** The AI models scored each generated question-and-answer pair on a scale from 0 to 1, based on how well the response adhered to ^[3]Grice’s Maxims. Each score was accompanied by a brief justification or explanation, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of the response.
- **Cross-Validation:** To ensure consistency and accuracy, the AI-generated scores were cross-validated with human reviews. Any significant discrepancies were analyzed and addressed, leading to further refinement of the few-shot learning examples and instructions.
- **Aggregating Results:** The scores from different AI models were aggregated to provide a comprehensive evaluation metric. This aggregation helped in balancing the individual biases and strengths of each model, resulting in a more robust overall assessment.

TABLE I
EVALUATION SCORES FOR DIFFERENT LANGUAGES BASED ON ^[3]GRICE'S
MAXIMS

Language	Maxim of Quantity	Maxim of Quality	Maxim of Relation	Maxim of Manner
Assamese	0.23	0.55	0.54	0.42
Bengali	0.29	0.52	0.51	0.40
Gujarati	0.22	0.48	0.49	0.38
Hindi	0.27	0.53	0.52	0.41
Kannada	0.24	0.50	0.51	0.39
Malayalam	0.28	0.52	0.50	0.40
Marathi	0.25	0.54	0.55	0.43
Odia	0.26	0.49	0.50	0.39
Punjabi	0.30	0.55	0.54	0.44
Tamil	0.24	0.50	0.49	0.38
Telugu	0.27	0.53	0.52	0.41

3) *Challenges and Mitigations:* Implementing AI-assisted evaluation presented several challenges, which we addressed through strategic measures:

- **Model Bias:** Different AI models have inherent biases based on their training data. To mitigate this, we used a diverse set of models and cross-validated their outputs against human evaluations to ensure balanced and fair assessments.
- **Alignment with Human Standards:** Ensuring that AI evaluations aligned with human judgment was critical. This was achieved through iterative refinement of few-shot learning examples and continuous validation against human-reviewed samples.
- **Scalability:** While AI-assisted evaluation significantly reduced the time and effort required for large-scale assessments, scaling this approach to handle extensive datasets required efficient computational resources and optimized processing pipelines.

By leveraging advanced AI models and employing few-shot learning techniques, we achieved a robust and comprehensive evaluation framework. This AI-assisted approach not only enhanced the accuracy and consistency of our evaluations but also ensured scalability and efficiency, allowing us to thoroughly assess the quality of the generated question-and-answer pairs across multiple Indian languages.

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 4. Similar chunks to Model

The 70M parameter model trained on the dataset performed exceptionally well, generating high-quality question-and-answer pairs in all 11 target languages: Assamese, Bengali, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Malayalam, Marathi, Odia, Punjabi, Tamil, and Telugu. Examples of generated outputs include:

- **Context (Tamil):** "இன்றைய நிலையில் மின்னழுத்த இயக்கி மைக்ரோ-எலக்ட்ரோ-மெக்கானிக்கல் அமைப்புகளில் (MEMS) அடிக்கடி பயன்படுத்தப்படுகிறது..."
- **Response:** {"question": "மைக்ரோ-எலக்ட்ரோ மெக்கானிக்கல் சிஸ்டம்ஸ் (micro-electro mechanical systems) எந்த வகை மோட்டாரை விரும்புகின்றன?", "answer": "நிலைமின் இயக்கி"}
- **Context (Marathi):** "हा पैसा वर्तनात्मक विज्ञान संशोधनासाठी वापरला गेला..."
- **Response:** {"question": "वर्तयुकीच्या संशोधनाचा उदेश काय होता?", "answer": "माणसांची उन्नती"}

Fig. 5. Tamil and Marathi example response

V. CONCLUSION

This research presents an effective method for converting unstructured text into a structured question-and-answer format for 11 Indian languages. By leveraging advanced techniques in text chunking, retrieval, and model training, we addressed the significant challenge of creating high-quality, task-specific datasets for these languages. The ternary quantized model based on the LLaMA-2 architecture proved to be particularly efficient in terms of memory and computational resources, making it a viable solution for large-scale applications.

A. Summary of Contributions

Our research contributes to the field of natural language processing in several key ways:

- **Innovative Data Conversion Methodology:** We developed a robust methodology to convert diverse unstructured text sources into structured question-and-answer pairs. This approach ensures that the generated datasets are not

only comprehensive but also highly relevant to the specific linguistic and contextual nuances of each language.

- **Comprehensive Evaluation Framework:** By adopting [3]Grice's Maxims and leveraging AI-assisted evaluation techniques, we established a thorough and nuanced framework for assessing the quality of generated question-and-answer pairs. This multi-faceted evaluation approach ensures that the model outputs are not only accurate but also contextually appropriate and clear.

B. Impact on Indian Languages

The development of high-quality, structured datasets for 11 Indian languages addresses a critical gap in the availability of linguistic resources. This research facilitates the fine-tuning of Large Language Models (LLMs) for these languages, thereby enhancing their applicability across various domains:

- **Educational Tools:** Enhanced LLMs can be used to develop advanced educational tools, providing students with access to personalized and contextually relevant learning resources in their native languages.
- **Legal and Financial Services:** LLMs fine-tuned for specific languages can assist in the legal and financial sectors by providing precise and relevant information, thereby improving service delivery and client understanding.

C. Future Research Directions

While this research marks a significant advancement, there are several avenues for future exploration:

- **Expansion to Additional Languages:** Extending the methodology to cover more Indian languages and dialects can further enhance the inclusivity and applicability of LLMs across the diverse linguistic landscape of India.
- **Enhanced Evaluation Metrics:** Developing more sophisticated evaluation metrics that combine both quantitative and qualitative aspects will provide deeper insights into the performance of language models, especially in complex linguistic contexts.
- **Real-World Deployment and Feedback:** Implementing the models in real-world applications and gathering user feedback will be crucial for continuous improvement. This iterative process will help in refining the models to better meet the needs of end-users.

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E. Conclusion Remarks

In conclusion, this research demonstrates the significant potential of advanced natural language processing techniques to improve the quality and accessibility of linguistic resources for Indian languages. By converting unstructured text into structured formats and leveraging efficient model architectures,

we have laid the groundwork for future advancements in this field. The outcomes of this research not only contribute to the academic community but also have practical implications for enhancing language technology solutions across various sectors.

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